

NUTRITIONAL AND ANTINUTRITIONAL VALUES OF ARMYWORMS (*NOCTUIDAE*
SPODOPTERA SPP)

¹Abulude, F.O, ¹Ogunkoya M.O, ²Ogunleye R.O, ³Kayode, B.O and ⁴Osundare, F.O
¹Department of General Studies, ³Department of Crop Production, ⁴Department of Extension and
Management, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Ondo State
²Department of Zoology, University of Ado Ekiti, Ado Ekiti, Ekiti State

ABSTRACT

The nutrition and antinutrition of *Noctuidae spodoptera spp* were examined using standard methods of analyses. From the results, it was found out that protein content of the caterpillar was high (mean value, 24.30 %), while fat, NFE, moisture, ash and fibre ranged thus mean value (%): 1.22, 48.33, 22.70, 1.88 and 1.58. Sodium (662.20 mgkg⁻¹), Calcium (415.25 mgkg⁻¹) and Magnesium (345.28 mgkg⁻¹) were relatively high. Nickel (2.42 mgkg⁻¹) was the least mineral present. The results also showed that the sample consist on antinutrients. It would be recommended that adequate processing should be ensured before consumption.

KEYWORDS: Nutrition, *Noctuidae spodoptera spp*, livestock, alternative source of protein, armyworms

INTRODUCTION

Armyworms are the caterpillars of various Noctuidae, mostly *spodoptera spp*, which under certain condition of high population density behave gregariously, swarms will march from field to field devastatingly, defoliating entire crops, most species are migratory as adults (Akinseye 2007)

The plants they attack are mostly Gramineae (Cereal and grasses), but the genus *spodoptera* is recorded feeding on plants from 40 different families containing at least 87 species of economic importance.

Armyworms pass the winter as a partially grown in the soil or under debris in grass area. Activity and growth are continuous except during very cold weather. When fully grown, they stop feeding for four days, then pupate over a 15-20 day period, Adult energy in May and June, mating takes place at night during the 5th hour after sunset (Pyke, 1979) multiple matings usually occur. Females feed for 7-10 days on honey, nectar or decaying fruit before laying eggs. Eggs are laid at night in clusters of 25-134 on grass and on small grain leaves. A single female may live as adult for days and produce up to 2000 eggs hatch in 6-10 days.

Armyworm caterpillars will vary in length from 2mm at first instance, larvae have strip as running the length of their body, one strip is present on each side and another stripe runs down the middle of the back.

The nutritional needs of most of the world population especially the developing nations remain unsatisfied. This has spurred on various researchers into studying the nutrient composition of both conventional and non conventional dietary items (Abdullahi, 2000). Improving the quality and quantity of livestock feeds have also been main concern of both researches and farms, hence efforts have been geared towards the utilization of lesser-known and under-utilized animals which are indigenous to Africa. From this angle, we have thought it fit to establish the nutritional status of the armyworms with a view of recommending their use as an alternative source of protein. It is therefore the aim of this study, is to quantify the proximate, mineral, oxalate, tannins and phytate compositions of armyworm (*Noctuidae spodoptera spp*). Further study is on to quantify fatty acid, amino acid and multienzyme digestibility of this sample.

Plate 1: *Noctuidae spodoptera spp* samples used for the analyses

Table 1: Proximate composition (%) of the samples analyzed (n=3)

Parameter	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of variation (%)
Protein	21.30	25.20	24.30	1.27	5.23
Fat	1.00	1.35	1.22	0.55	45.08
NFE	48.15	48.42	48.33	1.62	3.35
Moisture	22.10	23.00	22.70	0.71	3.13
Ash	1.52	2.10	1.88	0.50	26.60
Fibre	1.42	1.62	1.58	0.50	31.65

n= number of determinations, NFE= Nitrogen free extract

Table 2: Mineral composition (mgkg⁻¹) of the samples (n=3)

Parameter	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of variation (%)
Na	650.70	667.20	662.20	154.53	23.34
Fe	28.30	30.50	29.00	2.53	8.72
Mn	22.35	33.25	26.32	1.27	4.83
K	38.32	51.00	48.32	2.50	5.17
Zn	40.10	52.33	48.22	1.32	2.73
Cu	4.80	6.22	5.57	0.74	13.29
Ca	315.01	428.22	415.25	15.22	3.67
Ni	1.85	2.62	2.42	0.72	29.75
Mg	325.28	401.35	345.28	6.82	1.98

Table 3: Antinutritional contents of samples analyzed (n=3)

Parameter	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of variation (%)
(mgg ⁻¹)					
Tannins	50.25	72.10	60.35	2.70	4.47
Phytate P	1.32	2.25	1.87	0.50	26.74
Phytate	2.06	3.51	2.32	1.00	43.10
Oxalate	0.62	1.06	0.75	0.50	66.67

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample preparation.

Armyworms (*Noctuidae spodoptera spp*) (Plate 1) used for this study was obtained at Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. The samples were collected between July and August 2007.

They were washed in distilled water, sun dried for 10 days, ground in a Kenwood blender, sieved with 2mm wire mesh and store in an air-tight container at an ambient temperature prior to analyses.

Mineral Composition.

Two grams of powdered sample was in a muffle furnace (550⁰C) for 3h, dissolved in 2M HCL, filtered and made up to 50cm³. Minerals were read using a Pye Unicam SP 9 spectrophotometer.

Proximate Composition

The ash, fiber and nitrogen free extract (NFE) compositions of the sample were determined using standard methods of AOAC (1990), protein content was determined using the micro-kjeldahl method. The percentage nitrogen was multiplied by 6.25 to obtain percentage protein.

Antinutritional Composition

Tannin

Tannin was determined by the quantitative method of Markkar and Goodchild (1996).

Phytate.

The procedure of Young and Greaves (1940) as modified by Abulude (2001) was used for extraction, precipitation and determination of phytate.

Oxalate

The procedure proffered by Day and Underwood (1986) was employed for the above determination.

All determinations were in triplicate. Results were statistically analyzed using mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation in percent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proximate compositions of the sample are shown in Table 1. All the determinations were on dry matter basis. The protein value was relatively high with mean value of 24.30% (\pm SD=1.27.CV%=5.23). The fat content was low ranging from 1.00-1.35%. The ash content was also low. Moisture and NFE were generally high in the sample.

The results obtained for the protein content in the study were lower than those recorded for Cuban Boa (60.20-66.80%) Ogunkoya *et al* 2006), Larva (66.09%; Ekpo & Onigbinde, 2005) and crab (28.69-87.57%; Adeyeye, 2002), but higher than 10.50-17.50% recorded for Bouillon cube (Akpanyung, 2005) and tree barks (3.65-14.18%; Abulude *et al* 2004). The level of protein may contribute substantially to the total, daily intake of proteins by humans and livestock. The low fat content may not contribute to the flavour if roasted or dried. The fat content obtained in this study is fat lower than the amount found in most conventional foods like beef, chicken, egg, herring, mackerel and milk (Pyke 1979). This implies that a 100g sample of the armyworm may not meet the caloric fat needs of humans and animals and would not allow it to contribute significantly as a source of non-visible oil to any diet in which it may be present.

The protein content would be very appropriate weaning food for young ones since the fibre content was low (1.42-1.62%), which means the protein may be liable to easy digestion. Where the fibre is relatively high, it has nutritional advantage as it will assist in reducing constipation and other attendant problems (Adeyeye 2000).

The moisture content was in the range covered by Olaofe *et al* (1998) for grasshopper and Abdullahi (2000) for fish, but higher than those reported for mushroom samples (Esiet and Kayode, 2007). The relatively high moisture will not assist in keeping quality since the sample will go bad in time.

Mineral contents (mgkg⁻¹) of armyworm are presented in Table 2. The mean values ranged thus Na(662.20), Na(29.00) Mn(26.32), K(48.32), Zn(48.22), Cu(5.57), Ca(415.25),Ni(2.42) and Mg(345.28).

These values compared with results obtained from the literatures cited. Elements both micro and macro have been reported to be useful to animals and humans (Abulude *et al* 2007). Insects are known to be rich sources of various macro and trace elements. These elements are probably accumulated for future use in adult exoskeletal and connective tissue synthesis (Ekpo and Onigbinde (2005).

Sodium is an extra cellular cation involved in the regulation of plasma volume, acid-base balance, nerve and muscle contraction, High dietary sodium has been associated with essential hypertension (Lathan 1997), Iron is an important trace element in the human body. It plays crucial roles in haemopoiesis, control of infection and cell mediated immunity (Bhaskaram 2001). The deficiency of iron has been described as the most prevalent nutritional deficiency, and non deficiency anemia is estimated to affect more than one billion people worldwide (Trowbridge and Martorelli, 2002). The consequences of iron deficiency include reduce work capacity, impaired body temperature and regulation, impairment in behaviour and intellectual performance, and decreased resistance to infections (Dixon *et al*, 2004).

Zinc is present in all tissues of the body (i.e both humans and animals) and is a component of more than 50 enzymes (Adeyeye 2000). Meat is the richest source of zinc in the diet and supplies one third to one-half of the total zinc intake of meat eaters. Zinc dietary deficiency has been found in adolescent boys. An estimated 20% of the world population is reported to be at risk of inadequate zinc intake (Hotz and Brown 2004). In Nigeria study has shown that zinc deficiency affects 20% of children less than five years, 28.1% of mothers and 43.9% of pregnant women (Dixon *et al* 2004).

The sample appeared to be a good source of magnesium, sodium and potassium. Magnesium is an activator of many enzyme systems and maintains the electrical potential in nerves (Shils, 1973). Potassium is primarily an intracellular cation, in large part this cation is bound to protein and with sodium influences osmotic pressure and contributes to normal pH equilibrium. Plants and animals tissues are with sources of potassium this dietary lack is seldom found. Sodium is widely distributed in foods with the plants containing less than animal tissues.

CONCLUSION

The study shows that armyworms contain substantial amount of protein, carbohydrate and moisture which may contribute to the daily intake of these nutrients. The low levels of the antinutrients may be advantageous because they may not hinder the availability of the essential nutrients to consumers. However it is recommended that proper processing method should be put in place or used for the antinutrients to be destroyed or removed.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi S.A. (2000): Nutrient composition of three species of mormyrids in the Nigerian fresh water Nig. J. Tech. Educ. 17(1& 2): 177-183.
- Abulude F.O., Adesanya W.O., Ogunkoya M.O., Elemide O.A. and Esiet E.E. (2007): Nutritional composition of Ogi and its by-product. Acta Alimentaria. 36(4): 489-493.
- Abulude F.O., Onibon V.O. and Oluwatoba F (2004): Nutritional and anti-nutritional composition of some tree barks Nig. J. Basic and Appl. Sci. 13:43-49.
- Abulude F.O. (2001): Mineral and phytate content of vegetable grown in Nigeria and calculation of their phytate: Zn and Ca: phytate molar ratio. Adv. Food Sci. 23(1): 366-39.
- Adeyeye E.I. (2002): Determination of the chemical composition of the nutritionally valueable parts of male and female West African fresh water crab *Sudananantes africanus*. Int. J. Food Sci. & Nutr. 53:189-196.

Adeyeye E.I. (2000): Determination of the elemental composition of the nutritionally valuable parts of male and female common West African fresh water crab *sudananautes africanus*. Int. J. Food Sci & Nutr. 47: 111-116.

Akinseye A. S. (2007): The proximate, elemental, oxalate, phytate and tannin composition of armyworms (*Noctuidae spodoptera spp*). National Diploma Thesis, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Akpanyung E.O. (2005): proximate and mineral element composition of bouillon cubes produced in Nigeria. Pakistan J. Nutr. 4(5): 327-329.

AOAC (1995): official methods of Analysis. 5th edition, Washington D.C. Association of Official Analytical Chemists pg 6-16.

Bhaskaram P (2001): Immunobiology of mild nutrient deficiencies. Br. J. Nutr. 85:s75-s80.

Dixon B.M., Akinyele I. O, Oguntona S. Nokue R.A., Sanusi and Harris E.M (2004): Nigeria food consumption and nutrition survey 2001-2003 summary IITA, Ibadan,

Ekpo K. E and Onigbide A.O (2005); Nutritional potentials of larva of *Rhynchoplorus phoenicis* (F) Pakistan J. Nutr. 4(5): 287-290.

Esiet E. E. and Kayode B. O. (2007): Proximate composition and economic feasibility of some mushroom consumed in southwestern Nigeria. Cont. J. Food Sci & Tech. 1(3): 7-10.

Hotz C and Brown K.H (2004): International zinc nutrition consultative group (IZINCG). Technical Document No 1. Assessment of the risk of zinc deficiency in populations and options for its control. Food and Nutrition Bull. 25:s130-s162.

Latham M.C. (1997): Human nutrition in the developing world. FAO Foods and Nutrition Ser. No 29, Rome.

Makker M and Goodchild G (1996): The similarity between oxalic present in leaf and oxalate present in leaf and oxalate present in rat. Br. J. Nutr. 39(2): 233-414.

Ogunkoya M.O., Abulude F.O. and Oni A.B (2006): Determination of anatomical, proximate, minerals, oxalate, tannin and phytate compositions of Cuban Boa (*Epicrates anquifer*). Electr. J. Environ, Agric., and Food Chem. 5 (1):1661-1166.

Olaofe O. Arogundade L. A., Adeyeye E.I and Falusi O.N (1998): Composition and food properties of the variegated grasshopper, *Zonocerus variegatus*. Trop. Sci. 36:233-237.

Pyke M. (1979): The science of nutrition. In: Science in nutrition. John Murray (Publishers) Ltd, London pp 251-258.

Shils M.E. (1973): Magnesium. In modern nutrition in health and disease, eds RS Goodhart and M. E.Shils, Ch 6, Sect. B. Philadelphia P. A: Lea and Ferbigier.

Trowbridge F and Martorell R (2002): Forgoing effective strategies to combat iron deficiency. Summary and Recommendations. J. Nutr. 85: s75-s80.

Young S.M. and Greaves J. S. (1940): Influence of variety and treatment of phytin content of wheat. Food Res. 5:103-5.

Abulude, F.O *et al*: Continental J. Food Science and Technology 2: 44 - 49, 2008

Received for Publication: 08/01/2008

Accepted for Publication: 13/09/2008

Corresponding Author

Abulude, F.O

Department of General Studies, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Ondo State.